
Deliverable D3.6
**Fellowship programme, governance structure and business
model for SWForum.eu – v1**

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Abstract:	This deliverable is the first of a set of deliverables presenting the results from the work of task T3.3 - Definition and creation of a Governance structure and business model. It presents an overview of the governance structures offered by organizations similar to the one SWForum.eu would like to achieve (the Forum). Moreover, it presents the Fellowship programme, its call for participation and definition of selection criteria. Later deliverables of this series will be dedicated to the Forum governance structure, decision mechanisms, conflict resolution, membership types and so on, as well as the first set of potential business models. The second release will dig deeper into these issues and will present the final structure and agreements reached. This second release will also include the exploitation plans of SWForum.eu.
Keyword List:	Fellowship programme, organization of the Forum, governance structure
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Terms and abbreviations

CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
SW	Software
SWForum.eu	European Forum of the software research community

Executive Summary

This deliverable constitutes the first result produced by task T3.3 - Definition and creation of a Governance structure and business model - in the context of the SwForum project. The main objective of the task is to define the approach, governance structure and business model for the Forum of researchers that constitutes one of the main results of the project. This Forum will be based on two main ingredients: the participation to the Forum of well-known fellows in the European panorama of software engineering and a governance structure and business model that will set the basis for the self-sustainability of the Forum beyond the lifetime of the project. Consistently with these objectives, the purpose of this deliverable is twofold. On the one side, it defines the strategy we aim at adopting for involving new fellows in the work of the Forum. On the other side, it presents the landscape analysis performed by the SwForum consortium in the area of various types of scientific and technical associations in the area of Information Technology. The purpose of this analysis is to learn from other experiences and identify the best strategy to build a self-sustainable association.

The deliverable starts with an introduction (Section 1) where context and objectives are set. Section 2 defines the preliminary objectives of the Forum. Section 3 presents the analysis of the associations we have considered. Section 4 presents the preliminary lessons learnt. Section 5 defines the strategy for the fellowship programme. Finally, Section 6 draws the conclusions and defines a plan for the next steps for Task 3.3 and for the new versions of this deliverable.

1. Introduction

The main objective of the SwForum project is to raise awareness and strengthen the competitiveness of the European Software Industry - including the underlying digital infrastructures together with the needed security mechanisms - by facilitating a sustainable European Forum for stakeholders representing scientific researchers, providers, developers, operators and policy-makers relevant to software technologies, digital infrastructures and cybersecurity, where assets (products, services, technologies) can be shared, lessons learned, and policies developed, and facilitating engagement in the development of a set of research and innovation roadmaps for the Future Secure Digital Continuum through an online platform.

Within this context, SwForum will promote EU cross-fertilization between the areas of software, digital infrastructures, and cybersecurity. This goal will be achieved by organizing a self-sustainable Forum (Objective 2 in the Grant Agreement) in the context of which workshops on specific cross-fertilization themes will be organized and will be driven toward the publication of joint papers, joint policy papers around the topics, the creation of new initiatives, and the launch of new ideas.

The aim is to create a living Forum that will involve, on a voluntary basis, individuals (researchers, industry representatives and end-users) interested in the future of EU research and innovation actions in the context of software technologies. In order to engage and increase stakeholder participation, SWForum.eu proposes to create a Fellowship programme, which will serve to maintain a fluid pool of experts from a balanced set of SWForum.eu target stakeholder groups. This group of high-profile, acknowledged experts in their respective domains will create an attractive “pull” effect on potential participants in these activities and events and maintain a high level of excellence in the interactions within the Forum. The Forum will contribute to the definition of the future European research roadmaps and will, in general, stay in touch with the commission to provide inputs, highlight needs from multiple stakeholders, and the like. SWforum.eu will promote the creation of this Forum, will drive it for the first period and, most importantly, it will drive the definition of a self-sustaining governance strategy and business model that will permit the sustainability of the organisation to survive beyond the end of the project.

1.1 About this deliverable

This deliverable constitutes the first result produced by task T3.3. The main objective of the task is to define the approach, governance structure and business model for the Forum of researchers that constitutes one of the main results of the project. This Forum will be based on two main ingredients: the participation to the Forum of well-known fellows in the European panorama of software engineering and a governance structure and business model that will set the basis for the self-sustainability of the Forum beyond the lifetime of the project.

Consistently with these objectives, the purpose of this deliverable is twofold. On the one side, it defines the strategy we aim at adopting for involving new fellows in the work of the Forum. On the other side, it presents the landscape analysis performed by the SWForum.eu consortium of various types of scientific and technical associations in the area of Information Technology. The purpose of this analysis is to learn from other experiences and identify the best strategy to build a self-sustainable association.

1.2 Document structure

This document is organized as follows:

- Section 2 presents the main characteristics of the Forum we aim at developing as a result of SWForum.eu
- Section 3 analyses the mission, organization and sustainability model of similar organizations
- Section 4 draws the conclusion of the analysis in the previous section and sets a set of preliminary steps for the definition of the Forum model and organization.
- Section 5 focuses on presenting the fellowship programme.
- Finally, Section 6 draws the conclusions and provides a timeline for the forthcoming activities.

2. Main characteristics of the Forum to be established

The Forum will be an organization aiming at facilitating networking and cooperation between European Projects and other relevant stakeholders in the area of software engineering. The specific goals of the Forum will be:

- to contribute to the definition of the future European research roadmaps in the area;
- to create cooperation opportunities between European Projects;
- to increase the visibility of European research and innovation initiatives in the area of software engineering;
- to foster the development of joint roadmaps and other publications;
- to facilitate the interaction of the European software engineering community with stakeholders from other relevant disciplines, e.g., security, cloud and edge computing, AI.

The Forum foresees at least two types of members:

- individuals, that is, research fellows interested in the area of software engineering and participating into the Forum in a direct form;
- organizations, participating in the Forum through a representative.

The SWForum.eu project is getting in touch with all the consortiums and organizations that could be potentially interested in participating in the Forum with the objective to have a first discussion workshop in the first months of 2021. This will start up the Forum constitution. Proper dissemination activities will be started in cooperation with WP4 in order to encourage other partners to join and participate in the discussion and networking activities. The creation of the fellowship programme will be another way to gather the attention of the community and to encourage participation in the Forum activities.

3. Analysis of similar organizations

This section aims to analyse existing organizations or initiatives that could serve to inspire the SWForum.eu governance structure and business model. The analysis includes different fellowship schemes, partnership levels and organizational models from organizations with different backgrounds, e.g. academic, private, public.

Both initiatives for individuals and for communities have been covered in the analysis.

3.1 Initiatives for individuals

3.1.1 ACM SIGs

ACM¹ (Association for Computing Machinery) is the largest computing society in the world and brings together individuals from academia, research and industry. The objective is to share resources, solicit discussions, tackle challenges relevant to the field. ACM supports the professional growth of its members by providing opportunities for life-long learning, career development, and professional networking.

ACM was originally founded in USA but currently more than 50% of its 100,000 members are residing in other countries. This has led to the establishment of Councils in Europe, India, and China, fostering networking opportunities that strengthen ties within and across countries and technical communities. Their actions enhance ACM's ability to raise awareness of computing's important technical, educational, and social issues around the world.

ACM is organized in 37 Special Interest Groups (SIGs). These are focused on specific topics, for instance, SIGSOFT is focusing on software engineering, SIGCHI on human-computer interaction, SIGMETRICS on measurement and verification. New SIGs are created over the time to reflect the growth of computing's discrete disciplines and technical communities. SIGs offer opportunities for networking with colleagues, drive innovation in their reference disciplines, publish newsletters and magazines, encourage excellence through multiple recognition programs, and organize conferences and activities on a local-to-global scale.

At the top level, there are a few cross-cutting working groups, which include the one on ethics that has developed the well-known ACM Code of Conduct and the one on diversity and inclusion. SIGs, instead, focus on specific themes.

The development of ACM and of its SIGs is mostly based on the work of its volunteers. They can take a number of roles ranging from being Editor in Chief, Associate Editor and Reviewer for the ACM journals to being responsible for webinars or even taking a leading role in the governance of the whole organization, by serving in the ACM Council or in the ACM Executive Committee. SIGs mirror the same organization and are guided by an Executive Committee that remains on duty for two years.

Both ACM and the specific SIGs self-sustain with subscription fees and with the services they offer. The two main ACM services today are:

- The Digital Library which includes all publications edited by ACM and references also publications by other editors. The Digital Library represents an important source of knowledge for researchers and practitioners and offer sophisticated querying mechanisms to simplify bibliographic searches.

¹ <https://www.acm.org/>

- The sponsorship of conferences. ACM takes the financial risk in the organization of selected scientific conferences. The selection is performed in collaboration with the relevant SIGs. ACM typically pays the bills for the conference and acquires any income, distributing a portion of it in the budget of the corresponding SIGs.

ACM incomes are then composed of the following elements: the subscription fees payed by each individual member, the fees organizations pay to get access to the digital library, the income from conferences.

3.1.2 IEEE Special Interest Groups

IEEE² (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers) sponsors a series of Special Interest Groups (SIGs) much like those of the ACM. The individual groups are volunteer-driven – there is no paid personnel of any specific individual group.

Most of the SIGs in IEEE appear to be at a secondary level of organization. At the primary level are the Technical Committees (TC), which have their own organization, and could also provide insights about potential SWForum.eu governance models. The memberships are generally free.

As a specific example of TC activities, the TC on Business Informatics and Systems “[...] organizes and sponsors professional meetings, sets guidelines for educational programs, and helps nurture partnerships across academia, industry, and government agencies.”

As another example, the IEEE Technical Committee on Green Communications & Computing hosts no fewer than seven SIGs. Each SIG has a Chair and possibly multiple vice-chairs, plus possible advisors. The IEEE SIG on Green Smart Grid Communications has two characteristics of note:

- It lists a very comprehensive set of sub-areas of interest (much like what is seen in Calls for Papers at conferences), gathered from the members. This list serves to stimulate further interest in participation by potential members;
- It sponsors discussion groups on LinkedIn. This underlines the utility of providing a Forum for the exchange of ideas within the community involved in the SIG.

A further example is the Technical Committee on Data Engineering. It exists since 1998 and has a complete set of bylaws that constitute a governance. It has several types of activities that provide inputs to possible SWForum.eu initiatives.

- A very comprehensive set of conferences on data engineering;
- A regular publication (“Data Engineering Bulletin”) including a full editorial staff (volunteers);
- A program of awards (Rising Star, Impact, Education, Service)

A very recently founded SIG is IEEE SIGHT – Special Interest Group on Humanitarian Technology – which has a focus on technology for sustainable development. This is an outgrowth of an initiative that began in 2011, launched in India by the former IEEE Humanitarian Ad Hoc Committee Chair. The SIG was then founded in 2019 through a petition to the original SIGHT initiative.

The organization of the SIG is rather specific to its purpose (assistance to local areas in emerging nations, in particular), and therefore it is unclear how generalizable it can be to the SWForum.eu context. For example, key leaders are expected to reside in the local geographic areas in which

² <https://www.ieee.org/>

the SIG is operating – something that makes perfect sense within the mission of the SIG but appears less applicable to the context of SWForum.eu.

Nevertheless, there are aspects of its organization and sustainability model that provide a useful contribution to the discussion around SWForum.eu SIG governance. One aspect is education:

*“For SIGHT and its volunteers to be both effective and sustainable,
continuous training and education is essential.”*

The idea of continuing education as a tool for attaining sustainability is interesting also for SWForum.eu. IEEE SIGHT hosts a “virtual classroom”, which is essentially a series of webinars on pertinent topics.

The SIG also has funding available, which it receives from the SIGHT initiative. It uses these for specific funding of individual SIGHT sub-initiatives. It also provides much information on how to seek further funding – although much of this has to do with the specific objectives of SIGHT helping local development areas.

The overall governance is a committee of members, each of which leads a subcommittee on more specific topics.

A “SIGHT Group” (which is essentially a SIG) must be formed initially by at least six people. The six founders must be IEEE members, but others do not have to be.

Membership is free (no fees), and time commitments are entirely voluntary. Any travel expenses must be paid by the member.

3.1.3 RSE-The Society of Research Software Engineers

The Society of Research Software Engineers³ was launched in March 2019 as a charitable incorporated organisation that replaced the UK Research Software Engineers Association, itself established in 2013. The RSE community collaboration started informally in the Collaboration Workshops held by the “The Software Sustainability Institute”⁴ in 2012. In one of these workshops the attendees discussed about the lack of careers for software developers in academia and from there a new role in research was identified: The Research Software Engineer or RSE.

In the first RSE workshop in 2013, 56 self-identified RSEs met to discuss the role and the challenges of software developers in academia. Following a vote at the workshop, the UK Research Software Engineers Association was founded to represent RSEs, and the Association became democratic following elections for a new committee.

In 2016, the first RSE conference was held and the creation of related movements in countries around the world, starting in Germany then growing to the Netherlands, Nordic RSE, Australia and New Zealand, and the US.

³ <https://society-rse.org/about/>

⁴ <https://www.software.ac.uk/>

RSE is organised in RSE groups comprising a number of RSEs that work for researchers across an organisation and a Research Software Group Leaders Network was established in 2016. A Group Leaders' meeting is held twice a year where specific topics and best practices in RSE are discussed. RSE Leaders also have a dedicated slack channel in the ukrse slack which is open to all leaders from any country and used for discussions on a wide range of challenge.

RSE fellows are a group of individuals who work with researchers to gain an understanding of the problems they face to then develop, maintain and extend software to provide solutions. These fellows are selected through call for proposals and are paid for their support.

Regional RSE Groups have the aim of creating a skills network, a local hub for advice. Currently there exist two RSE groups in the UK: Research Software London and N8CIR RSE Community.

International RSE communities started to be part of the RSE network with the de-RSE from Germany, the first non-UK association to be launched. There are now various associations around the world, including countries like New Zealand, Belgium, Netherlands or the USA.

The trustees of the society are elected directly by the membership for two-year terms with half being up for re-election or replacement each year.

A member in RSE can be an individual, a corporate body, or an individual or corporate body representing an organisation which is not incorporated. There are two types of members, a) full members or voting members who pay an annual membership fee of 20 £ or b) informal or associate non-voting members, who do not pay a fee.

3.2 Initiatives for industrial and academic organizations

3.2.1 IFIP

IFIP⁵ (International Federation for Information Processing) is a multinational, apolitical non-profit organization in Information and Communication Technologies and Science established in 1960 under the auspices of UNESCO. Its mission is to achieve the worldwide professional and socially responsible development and application of ICT.

Membership is open to national and international ICT societies, plus professional associations, scientific academies, etc. in the ICT field. Currently, IFIP members includes 36 countries (of which 18 out 27 EU members), 2 other national members, and 2 international members.

From an organizational standpoint, the main bodies of the federation are: general assembly, board, and executive committee.

- The *General Assembly* is composed of one representative from each Country Representative Member, Member at Large and Associate Member and of Honorary Members. During their terms, also TC chair will participate to the general assembly. The General Assembly is the supreme authority of the Federation. The General Assembly shall determine fundamental policy, adopt the programme of activity, hear and approve the reports of any substructures it may have established, decide on admission and exclusion of Members, elect Officers and Councilors, adopt and revise Statutes and Bylaws, adopt the budget, review the expenditures and accept the audit reports. General Assembly also decides the substructure.

⁵ <https://www.ifip.org/>

- The *Board* is composed of the Executive Committee and Councillors which are elected by the General Assembly.
- *Executive Committee* is elected by the General Assembly among its Country Representative Members, Members at Large and Ex-Officio Members. IT is composed by a President, four Vice-Presidents, a Honorary Secretary and a Honorary Treasurer.

Currently, IFIP is organized around 13 Technical Committees (TCs) focused on a specific topic, namely:

- TC 1: Foundations of Computer Science
- TC 2: Software: Theory and Practice
- TC 3: Education
- TC 5: Information Technology Applications
- TC 6: Communication Systems
- TC 7: System Modeling and Optimization
- TC 8: Information Systems
- TC 9: Relationship between Computers and Society
- TC 10: Computer Systems Technology
- TC 11: Security and Protection in Information Processing Systems
- TC 12: Artificial Intelligence
- TC 13: Human-Computer Interaction
- TC 14: Entertainment Computing

Each TC is organized in Working Groups (WGs) which are in charge of organizing conferences, meetings and stimulating the organization of networking activities involving the members as well as external communities. Role of the TCs is to supervise the activities of the related WG and to promote traversal activities.

Individual memberships are at WG level. Although each WG could have different policies in admitting new members, most of the WGs requires the participation to at least two annual meeting of a WG as auditor before to apply for the membership. The application is considered during the annual TC meeting where all the WG chair participate and the CVs of the applicants are analysed.

Fees are required to all the members. In addition, when a WG or TC organize an event under the sponsorship of IFIP, a fee is required for every attendant to the event.

3.2.2 Informatics Europe

Informatics Europe⁶ is a European no-profit organization established in Zurich in 2005. Its goal is to represent the academic and research community in Informatics in Europe. “Bringing together university departments and research laboratories, it creates a strong common voice to safeguard and shape quality research and education in Informatics in Europe. With over 140 member institutions across 33 countries, Informatics Europe promotes common positions and acts on common priorities.”

Today the association offers to its members the following services:

- *A Forum for exchange of ideas*: every year, Informatics Europe organizes ECSS (The European Computer Science Summit) where representatives from university departments reconvene to attend high profile keynotes and to network and discuss on important topics related to the organization of department, to high level education, to

⁶ <https://www.informatics-europe.org/>

funding opportunities, and the like. The association also organizes other satellite events on specific topics, either as part of the main conference or through the year. One of the important events of this kind aims at creating a network between the National Associations focusing on Informatics. Finally, the association promotes and coordinates permanent working groups focusing on specific subjects. One of these is focusing on the role of women in informatics research and education.

- *Data and insights on the status of high level education on Informatics in Europe:* Informatics Europe collects every year numerical information about the situation of students (enrolled, graduates, gender, ...) and professors (number of faculties per department, number of faculties per role, gender, salary, ...) in almost all countries in Europe and makes the available for further analyses.
- *Support to the evaluation of university departments in Informatics:* Informatics Europe has defined an assessment process and supports university departments in performing an internal evaluation. The outcome of such evaluation is a set of practical recommendations for improving the quality and the impact of the departmental activities.
- *Awards:* Traditionally, Informatics Europe awards best practices in education and initiatives aiming at ensuring support to diversity in Informatics careers.
- *Online resources:* These are a research and education directory, a job platform, a newsletter, and a LinkedIn discussion group.

Informatics Europe organization is centered around the two following institutions:

- *The General Assembly:* this is constituted by representatives of all members of the association. The General Assembly meets yearly and elects the members of the Board of Directors
- The *Board of Directors* composed of at most eleven Members-at-Large, elected by the Annual General Assembly, for a term of two years; A President, two Vice Presidents and a Treasurer, elected under the same modalities; Ex officio: the Past President, if any, for the term immediately after his or her President's term; Ex officio: the head of the professional staff of Informatics Europe.

The members of the Board of Directors are all volunteers, the only exception is the head of the professional staff who is a paid employee of the organization, together with a few other members of the staff.

The sustainability model of the association is based on the fees paid yearly by the members and on the income deriving from ECSS and the other meetings organized through the year. The association is also participating in projects funded either by the European Commission or by private companies and aiming at a specific objective.

3.2.3 Big Data Value Association

The Big Data Value association (BDVA)⁷ is an industry -driven association with more than 200 members, ranging from large organizations to small ones as well as research organizations. The Big Data Value Association is the private part of the Big Data Value PPP⁸.

The origins of the Big Data Value Association stem from the Coordination and Support Action (CSA) BIG⁹, which had as main goal to build “*an industrial community around Big Data in Europe*” by “[...] *setting up the necessary collaboration and dissemination infrastructure to link*

⁷ <https://www.bdva.eu/about>

⁸ The public part is the European Commission

⁹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/318062/es>

technology suppliers, integrators and leading user organizations”. The Big Data Public Private Forum, one of the main results of the project, aimed at defining and implementing a strategy for research and innovation, as well as boosting the big data economy. This evolved into the Big Data Value Association, which was launched in 2014.

The BDVA plays an important role in defining the research roadmap in topics related to Big Data and Artificial intelligence.

The BDVA is composed of the following different types of memberships¹⁰:

1. *Full members*: they can participate in all activities of the association, have full voting rights in the General Assembly (see below), can be part of the Board of Directors (see below).
2. *Associate members*: they can participate in the activities of the association by they do not have any voting rights.

Both types of membership have an annual membership fee¹¹ layered on the type of organisation (Large, SME, academia, other), and that of as 2020 are as follows:

	Full Members	Associate Members
Large Industry	9.500 €	2.500 €
Small or Medium Enterprise	1.500 €	500 €
Academia / Research	1.500 €	500 €
Others	1.500 €	500 €

Figure 1. Membership annual fees for the Big Data Value Association (source: BDVA¹²)

The operational structure of the BDVA is organized in task forces that provide a response to a specific activity within the objectives of the association. These are overseen by the Board of Directors. The existing task forces (as of December 2020) are as follows:

Figure 2. Big Data Value Association Governance structure (source: BDVA¹³)

- TF1 Programme: Provides inputs to the H2020 Programme content of the BDV PPP

¹⁰ https://www.bdva.eu/Become_a_member

¹¹ <https://www.bdva.eu/sites/default/files/Information%20about%20membership%20fees%202020.pdf>

¹² <https://www.bdva.eu/sites/default/files/Information%20about%20membership%20fees%202020.pdf>

¹³ <https://www.bdva.eu/task-force-overview>

- TF2 Impact: Monitors the impact KPIs defined for the PPP
- TF3 Community: Big data community engagement and participation
- TF4 Communication: Communication activities to create awareness around the association (BDVA)
- TF5 Policy and Societal: closing the gap between big data technologies and legal, societal and policy matters
- TF6 Technical: identification of the technical challenges of the programme
- TF7 Application: Group(s) that are domain-related and that can influence the other task forces.
- TF8 Business: Business and economic influences and business areas such as Web Entrepreneurs and SMEs
- TF9 Skills and Education: Skills needed for all aspects related to big data and artificial intelligence.

Under each Task force, several sub-groups, more focused, also exist. The results of these sub-groups are position papers, whitepapers, memorandum of understanding, and so on.

The Governance structure of the BDVA is depicted in the next figure:

Figure 3. Big Data Value Association Governance structure (source: BDVA¹⁴)

The different bodies are as follows:

- The *General Assembly (GA)* is made of all the members of the BDVA, although only full members have voting rights. The GA approves the general policy of the association taking as input the proposals made by the Board of Directors and then provides recommendations to the Board of Directors for their application. The GA also elects the President, Vice President(s) and Treasurer.
- The *Board of Directors (BoD)* is selected by the General Assembly under a 2-year mandate. The BoD's goal is to reach the objectives defined by the Association, and follows the resolutions adopted by the GA.
- The *Partnership Board (PB)* is the monitoring body of the cPPP¹⁵ composed by a group of selected directors of the Board, and representatives of the European Commission.

¹⁴ <https://www.bdva.eu/about>

¹⁵ cPPP: Collaborative Public Private Partnership

- The **Secretary General** (SG) is responsible for the day-to-day administrative management of the Association with the support of the Deputy Secretary General and the BDVA Secretariat.

3.2.4 NESSI

NESSI, the Networked Software and Services Initiative¹⁶, is the European Technology Platform, that aims at promoting software, services and data as key enablers to solve the challenges, societal and economic, that exist in Europe.

NESSI is recognized as a European Technology Platform (ETP). According to the communication SWD(2013)272¹⁷, ETPs shall have a:

- Strategy function by developing strategies and providing analysis of research and innovation challenges and opportunities;
- Mobilising function, by bringing together industry and other stakeholders;
- Dissemination function, by sharing information and enabling transfer of knowledge to stakeholders.

NESSI promotes that software, services, and data are key enablers to help resolve European societal and economic challenges across all sectors, both private and public, such as manufacturing, transportation, energy, and healthcare.

NESSI publishes position papers and contributes to the definition of the work programme of the European Commission with both position papers and Strategic Research and Innovation Agendas.

According to the website, there are no distinct thematic or working groups as such. All members can participate in the creation of position papers and Strategic Research and Innovation Agendas through the NESSI Board (see next).

Currently 24 organisations are part of NESSI. There are in principle no task forces or subgroups. As the above-mentioned communication states, each ETP shall define its governance structure. In the case of NESSI it is as follows¹⁸:

- *NESSI Board*: all members are part of the NESSI board and provide some financial support for the operations;
- *NESSI Steering Committee* is the body responsible for the definition, implementation and monitoring of NESSI activities.

The membership is free and is open to every organization that meets the following criteria: (i) is legally established; (ii) has a legal presence in Europe; (iii) is either an ICT SME, ICT Large organization, academia & Research or users. Apart from these three criteria, in order to become a member of NESSI the organization wishing to participate shall provide a letter of intent sharing the vision and mission of NESSI¹⁹.

NESSI seeks funding through the participation of the ETP in coordination and support actions, such as the NESSI 2010 Support Action ²⁰.

¹⁶ <http://www.nessi-europe.com/default.aspx?page=home>

¹⁷ http://nanofutures.eu/sites/default/files/SWD_2013_272_F1_STAFF_WORKING_PAPER_EN_V2_P1_735480.pdf

¹⁸ <http://www.nessi-europe.com/default.aspx?Page=organisation>

¹⁹ <http://www.nessi-europe.com/default.aspx?Page=joining>

²⁰ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/216967>

3.2.5 NEM-New European Media Initiative

The NEM Initiative²¹ (New European Media Initiative) was established as one of the European Technology Platform under the Seventh Framework Programme, aiming at fostering the convergence between consumer electronics, broadcasting and telecoms in order to develop the emerging business sector of networked and electronic media. To respond to the new needs and requirements of the Horizon 2020 programme, the NEM initiative enlarged its focus towards creative industries and changed its name from Networked an Electronic Media Initiative to New European Media, dealing with Connected, Converging and Interactive Media & Creative Industries, driving the future of digital experience.

The NEM members include major European organisations working in the networked and electronic media area, including content providers, creative industries, broadcasters, network equipment manufacturers, network operators and service providers, academia, standardisation bodies and government institutions.

NEM produces several documents (Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda, NEM vision, position papers and more) to generate impact and create awareness on the European Media industry.

The NEM General Assembly is constituted by all interested stakeholders. Membership is free and open to all. General Assembly members elect the NEM Steering Board and endorse the NEM Strategic Research Agenda (SRA) as well as the policies and content of the initiative. All members are welcome to participate in the GA meetings.

There are several NEM members types:

- *NEM Ambassadors*: The Ambassadors promote the NEM Initiatives in their region, represent their ecosystem at EU level and contribute to federating the European convergence and media landscape.
- *NEM Working Groups*: NEM comprises several working groups focused on specific themes or issues in Media and content. Some of these are: NGI (Next Generation Internet), Media DIH (Digital Innovation Hub), or 5G PPP.
- *NEM projects*: NEM also includes the EC funded projects from different units, conforming a cluster of projects.
- *International NEM*: NEM initiative is in partnership with several Clusters, associations, platforms.

The NEM governance is based on the following structure:

- *NEM General Assembly* consisting of all interested stakeholders – NEM members which are mainly public and private organisations.
- *NEM Steering Board* – involving a representative set of players of all domains of the Networked and Electronic Media, defining the strategic vision and the key orientations of the Initiative, aiming at converting the NEM vision into a strategic agenda, and setting the operational goals for achieving this agenda
- *NEM Executive Group* – a subset of the Steering Board who, together with NEM Office (funded through in-kind collaborations by the members and participation into projects funded by the EU), takes the responsibility for the day-to-day management of the activities of the initiative and the handling of all working relationships

²¹ <https://nem-initiative.org/>

3.2.6 European Open Science Cloud EOSC

The idea of the European Open Science Cloud²² (EOSC) was conceived back in 2015, and was officially launched in November 2018, with access to initial services via the EOSC Portal. EOSC aims to become Europe’s trusted virtual environment for potentially 1.7 million European researchers and 70 million professionals in science, technology, the humanities and social sciences to store, manage, analyse and re-use data for research, innovation and educational purposes, as well as to support EU science in its global leading role. As its vision statement says:

“... to give Europe a global lead in scientific data infrastructures and to ensure that European scientists reap the full benefits of data-driven science.”

Given its large, pan-European nature, the organisers of EOSC decided that it would be best served by the establishment of a legal entity not only to further its primary aims, but also to handle practical matters such as finances and the hiring of dedicated staff. Therefore, a non-profit organisation was founded, with its seat in Belgium (presumably because of its close association with the European Commission, located in Brussels). Formally it is an AISBL (*Association internationale sans but lucratif*) – that is, an International Non-Profit Organization. Officially it is named the “European Open Science Cloud Association” or simply “EOSC Association”.

Being a formally constituted organisation, the EOSC Association benefits from the availability of a set of Statutes, in which the usual rules may be specified, such as: membership rules and types, fees, termination / resignation, limited liability; governance structure including general assembly, voting rules including quorum; Board of Directors, roles such as President, Vice-President, and Treasurer; Secretariate; General provisions such as conflict resolution; Operational and Advisory Bodies.

The overall governance structure described in the Statutes is further detailed in the EOSC Portal, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. EOSC Governance (source: EOSC²³)

As Figure 4 shows, the overall governance contains many of the elements envisioned in SWForum.eu, albeit at a larger scale.

²² <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/>

²³ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-governance>

The *Strategic Layer* is the Board, determining the direction on the evolution of the overall EOSC. It is roughly equivalent to the PMB of SWForum.eu.

The Executive Layer contains the Executive Board, which oversees the concrete implementation of EOSC. What is especially interesting here is that it specifically cites “Working Groups”. The “operational bodies” mentioned in the Statutes are in fact named Working Groups and sometimes Task Forces in the EOSC Association. (Whereas the “advisory bodies” of the Statutes are what we normally see as “External Advisory Groups” or the like in Horizon2020 projects.)

The *Working Groups* within the Executive Layer of the EOSC Association are relatively high level and dedicated to specific aspects of implementing EOSC but could contribute indications of the kind of areas in which a SWForum.eu structure would want to establish task forces and similar groups. In the following, some of the current Working Groups are discussed:

- *Landscape*. This WG maps the current ecosystem of research infrastructures, looking for candidates for inclusion in EOSC. (One could imagine a similar task force in SWForum.eu, looking for candidates to include in the Forum.)
- *FAIR*. Recalling that EOSC is founded on the principle of FAIR data, a WG is entirely dedicated to working out the requirements based on the principle for fostering the needed interoperability in EOSC. (Here, too, one could imagine a WG in SWForum.eu that would be dedicated to working out the principles upon which the Forum is founded, such as promotion of open source, improving competitiveness, etc.)
- *Architecture*. EOSC is a federation of systems, so it needs a technical framework enabling this federation. It is not clear how this would transfer to SWForum.eu.
- *Rules of participation*. This WG concerns the rights and duties of operators and users in EOSC transactions (recall that EOSC is intended as a working platform for scientific data storage and retrieval).
- *Skills and Training*. The purpose of this WG is to define a sustainable training infrastructure to help ensure EOSC uptake. The idea of groups dedicated to training appears to be a thread running through all successful SIGs that have been observed over the course of the studies in this deliverable.
- *Sustainability*. This is a WG dedicated entirely to the topic of an “operational, scalable, and sustainable EOSC.” The relevance to SWForum.eu is self-evident.

The other two components of the EOSC governance are the **Stakeholder layer** and **CSA Structure**. The CSA structure is nothing other than the corresponding CSA project (*EOSC Secretariat*), whereas the Stakeholder layer involves the implementation of their own forum, similar in nature to the Living Forum of SWForum.eu.

The EOSC Stakeholder Forum organises two major events per year (the *EOSC Symposium* and the *EOSC Event*). They regularly draw very large audiences.

3.2.7 European Clusters

In 2015 four Clusters of European Projects on Cloud have been created²⁴. Their goal was to create an environment where projects funded by the European Community (in particular, the recipients of ICT7 and ICT9 H2020 grants) could interact and find synergies among each other. Each cluster had set specific goals but all of them focus on collaboration among members on technical aspects as well as on the identification of trends in the relevant markets and on

²⁴ <https://eucloudclusters.wordpress.com/2019/09/30/eu-projects-clusters/>

engaging in innovative ways to address such trends. The clusters that were defined at the time were the following:

- Software Engineering for Services and Applications
- Future Cloud Cluster
- Novel approaches and technologies for resource and service management
- Data Protection, Security and Privacy in the Cloud

All the four clusters have been running based on the work of a group of volunteers and have created results in terms of shared discussion meetings, roadmaps and peer to peer collaborations between groups of partners.

Over the time, all of them have faced the difficulty of not having a well-defined organizational structure. This difficulty has resulted in the fact that their lifetime has been depending on the availability of the initial organizing group. At the moment, one of them, constituted from the merge of the Future Cloud Cluster and the Novel approaches and technologies for resource and service management cluster, is active and is producing a new roadmap.

3.2.8 AI Alliance

The European AI Alliance is “a forum engaged in a broad and open discussion of all aspects of Artificial Intelligence development and its impacts”²⁵, launched by the European Commission in June 2018 as part of the European Strategy on Artificial Intelligence.

The European AI Alliance, a multi-stakeholder forum, had as initial goal, to provide feedback to the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI HLEG)²⁶. The AI HLEG was a group of experts appointed by the Commission following the launch of a European AI strategy in April 2018. The initial goal of the AI Alliance is now extended, and members can now contribute with discussions, documents, and debates into the policy aspects demanded by the European Commission.

The mandate of the AI HLEG ended in July 2020, but the community created under this umbrella continued its activity.

According to the European Commission’s site over 4000 members are part of the AI Alliance, with participants ranging from businesses to consumer organizations, trade unions, academia, and so on²⁷. The platform is hosted in the “Futurium” platform²⁸ run and maintained by the Commission. Anyone can be a member, although upon approval by the European Commission.

The community gets together yearly in what it is called the “European AI Alliance Assembly”. At the time of writing this deliverable there have been two editions of the Assembly, the first one in June 2019²⁹ and the second one in October 2020³⁰.

Approved members can access the AI Alliance platform can interact with the AI HLEG which functions as the Steering Group.

There is no formal structure in the AI Alliance. Finally, there is no membership fee to be part of the AI Alliance platform.

²⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/european-ai-alliance>

²⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/high-level-group-artificial-intelligence>

²⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/european-ai-alliance>

²⁸ <https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en>

²⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/european-ai-alliance>

³⁰ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/second-european-ai-alliance-assembly>

3.2.9 Horizon Europe partnerships

European Partnerships³¹ are initiatives where the European Commission, together with private and public partners, aims to support the development and implementation of a programme of research and innovation activities, in this case the Horizon Europe programme. The involved partners can represent industry, universities, research organisations, local, regional, national or international public bodies or civil society organisations, including foundations and NGOs.

The aim of European partnerships with European Union and associated countries, the private sector, foundations and other stakeholders is to go through global challenges and modernise industry.

The Horizon Europe³² proposal lays down the conditions and principles for establishing European Partnerships. There are 3 types.

- *Co-programmed European Partnerships*: These are partnerships between the Commission and private and/or public partners. They are based on memoranda of understanding and/or contractual arrangements.
- *Co-funded European Partnerships using a programme co-fund action*: Partnerships involving EU countries, with research funders and other public authorities at the core of the consortium.
- *Institutionalised European Partnerships*: These are partnerships where the EU participates in research and innovation funding programmes that are undertaken by EU countries. These partnerships require specific legislative proposals from the Commission, and they are implemented by dedicated structures created for that purpose. They will only be implemented in the case that other HE partnerships or programmes would not achieve the expected objectives.
- *EIT Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs)* are also institutionalised partnerships. EIT KICs aim to address skills shortages and are already established under Horizon 2020. Key partners in EIT KICs are higher education institutions, research organisations, companies and other stakeholders.

The partnership candidates are organised across 5 thematic areas: Health; Digital Industry and Space; Climate, energy and mobility; Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment and Cross theme.

In the following figure 5, an overview of the current partnerships' candidates per type and thematic areas is shown:

³¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/horizon-europe/european-partnerships-horizon-europe_en

³² https://ec.europa.eu/info/horizon-europe/european-partnerships-horizon-europe_en

Figure 5. Partnerships candidates per thematic area and type. (Source: CDTI³³)

3.2.10 European Alliance on Industrial Data and Cloud

The European Alliance on Industrial Data and Cloud was announced on October 2020³⁴, after the memorandum of understanding between the 27 member states for the next generation of cloud for Europe. It is expected to be launched by the end of 2020 and will have as members, interested Member States, industries, as well as individual experts.

The goal of this Alliance is to “design the detailed business, investment and implementation plan to deploy the next generation cloud capacities for the public and private sector” and it is a direct response to the EU Data strategy released on February 2020.

The EU Data strategy invites the public and private sector to coinvest in the development of the cloud federation and common data spaces. The joint declaration signed by the Member states will focus on the following actions³⁵:

- Combine private, national and EU investment to deploy competitive, green and secure cloud infrastructures and services
- Define a common European approach for the federation of cloud capacities to foster pan-European interoperable European cloud services. Adherence to EU policies is key.
- Drive the adoption of more secure, interoperable, and energy-efficient cloud services for stakeholders such as SMEs, start-ups and the public sector.

As of December 2020, the governance model and the community are not known.

³³ <https://www.cdti.es/>

³⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/towards-next-generation-cloud-europe#:~:text=A%20European%20Alliance%20on%20Industrial,the%20end%20of%20the%20year.&text=All%2027%20Member%20States%20have,public%20sectors%20across%20the%20EU.>

³⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/towards-next-generation-cloud-europe#:~:text=A%20European%20Alliance%20on%20Industrial,the%20end%20of%20the%20year.&text=All%2027%20Member%20States%20have,public%20sectors%20across%20the%20EU.>

3.2.11 ECSO

The European Cyber Security Organisation (ECSO) ASBL is a fully self-financed non-for-profit organisation under the Belgian law, established in June 2016. ECSO is the private counterpart to the European Commission in implementing the contractual Public-Private Partnership (cPPP) on cybersecurity. ECSO unites a variety of European cybersecurity stakeholders across the EU Member States, the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) and H2020 Programme associated countries. The main goal of ECSO is to coordinate the development of the European Cybersecurity Ecosystem:³⁶

- **FEDERATE & CONNECT:** ECSO Federates the European Cybersecurity Public and Private Community and facilitates the networking and cooperation at European level
- **ACT:** ECSO Supports members' needs and market development in public-private cooperation with concrete actions/initiatives geared towards increasing strategic autonomy.
- **SUPPORT;** ECSO is a recognised actor in the European institutional landscape, it cooperates with European institutions, bodies and agencies as well as National Public administrations for the development and implementation of EU policies, programmes and legislations to increase digital autonomy.

ECSO maintains close collaboration with European Commissioners and top-level management of the European Commission's DGs including DG CNECT, DG RTD, DG ENER, DG MOVE, JRC, DG DIGIT, EEAS. Upon the invitation of the Presidency of the Council of the EU, ECSO is regularly invited to provide updates on the status of its work to the Horizontal Working Party on Cyber Issues of the Council. ECSO closely engages with Members of the European Parliament (MEPs), Committees and Political Groups providing independent assessments on European legislative proposals such as the implementation of the NIS Directive, the Cybersecurity Act including the establishment of a European Certification Framework and the definition of ENISA's new mandate, as well as the set-up of a European Cybersecurity Industrial, Technology and Research Competence Centre and the Network of National Coordination Centres. In parallel, ECSO fosters relations between MEPs and ECSO Members addressing key topics such as support to SMEs, regional development, R&I, investments, disruptive technologies, etc as well as ECSO Initiatives like Women4Cyber and Youth4Cyber.³⁷

ECSO regularly cooperates with European Agencies and Bodies such as ENISA (European Union Agency for Cybersecurity), EUROPOL (European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation), EDA (European Defence Agency), ESA (European Space Agency), EASA (European Aviation Safety Agency), EIT (European Institute of Innovation & Technology), EIB (European Investment Bank), CEN/CENELEC (European Committee for Standardisation/European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation), ETSI (European Telecommunications Standards Institute).

The Governance Structure of ECSO is based upon the General Assembly being the ultimate decision-making body - with the ECSO Board of Directors addressing the major issues related to policy and market actions. The ECSO Governing Bodies are below the Board of Directors and include a Coordination / Strategy Committee, a National Public Authorities Committee, a Scientific and Technologies Committee and a Financial, Ethics and Governance Committee. Six operational working groups come next within the governance structure with the General Assembly underpinning the whole of the organisation. The Secretariat supports the daily operations and running of the ECSO Association.

³⁶ <https://ecs-org.eu/about>

³⁷ Ibid

Figure 6. ECISO Governance structure (source ECISO³⁸)

ECISO Categories of Members are presented next.³⁹

- *Large companies*: developing and/or manufacturing cybersecurity solutions / services providers;
- *National and European Organisation / Associations*: representing interests at national or European / International level.
- *SMEs*; Associations composed only by SME, Start-ups, Incubators, Accelerators.
- *Users / Operators* National public administrations or private companies (large or SMEs) directly represented.
- *Regional / Local public administrations*; Regional / Local Clusters of public / private Legal Entities with local economic / ecosystem development interests.
- *Public Administrations* at national level.
- *Research Centers, Academia / Universities*; Associations composed only by Research Centers, Academia or Universities.
- *Others* (financing bodies, insurances, consultants, etc.).

ECISO has several working groups⁴⁰ and task forces⁴¹ aligned with the priorities defined by the Board of Directors. The working groups (WGs) are:

- *WG1: Standardisation, certification and supply chain management* contributes towards the support of trusted certified solutions. Among some of the key objectives include to understand the challenges of certification, create a roadmap for priorities and understand the meaning of harmonisation
- *WG2 Market Deployment, Investments and International Collaboration* has as main goal to contribute to the consolidation of the cybersecurity market

³⁸ <https://ecs-org.eu/about>

³⁹ <https://ecs-org.eu/membership>

⁴⁰ <https://ecs-org.eu/activities>

⁴¹ *ibid*

- *WG3: Sectoral Demand and Users Committee* seeks to engage with users to understand cybersecurity threats. This working group includes a users committee composed of users and operators of essential services (OES).
- *WG4: support to SMEs*, coordination with countries and regions has the goal of developing coordinated activities between regions, local bodies and clusters.
- *WG5: Education, Training, Awareness, Cyber Ranges* is focused on increasing the cybersecurity competences and capacity building of organizations.
- *WG6: SRIA and Cyber Security Technologies* aims at defining the roadmap of research and innovation in cybersecurity.

Two task forces and committees⁴² exist in addition to the above working groups:

- *Scientific & Technology Committee* centered in the scientific and technological aspects of cybersecurity.
- *NAPAC: National Public Administrations Committee*, composed of a set of public authority representatives that provide feedback to the activities and results generated by ECSO.

Finally, several initiatives have been launched by ECSO⁴³:

- *Women4Cyber* Initiative was launched to increase the participation of women in cybersecurity. This initiative has led into a Women4Cyber foundation⁴⁴.
- *Youth4Cyber* aims at raising awareness of cybersecurity in young people aged 6 – 26.
- *Cybersecurity Made in Europe Label, an industry* – driven marketing tool aimed at promoting European cybersecurity companies and increasing the visibility on the global market.
- *TransContinuum Initiative*: it encompasses several organizations such as AIOTI, 5G IA, BDVA, ETP4HPC, HIPEAC, CLARE and EU-Maths in, and has as main goal the collaboration of those entities focusing on different technology domains in the identification of priorities and recommendations for Research and Innovation, generate a discussion forum, foster an interdisciplinary network and contribute to Strategic Research and Innovation Agendas.

⁴² ibid

⁴³ ibid

⁴⁴ <https://women4cyber.eu/foundation>

4. Lessons learnt from the analysis and preliminary steps toward the organization of the Forum

Table 1 shows an overview of the analysed associations in terms of the following aspects: whether the association is a legal entity or not, the areas of interest, whether it is an association of individuals or of other organizations, how they obtain revenues, if any. These aspects have been selected as they constitute an important reference for shaping the structure of our Forum.

Table 1. Overview of the analyzed associations.

	Legal entity	Areas of interest	Members' nature	Revenues
ACM and ACM SIGs	Yes	Computer science and all its subfields	Individuals	Membership fees, conference execution, publications, digital library
IEEE and IEEE SIGs	Yes	Technology and all its fields	Individuals	Membership fees, conference execution, publications, digital library
RSE society	Yes	Software Engineering for research in all sectors	Individuals	Membership fees
IFIP	Yes	Information and Communication Technologies	ICT societies, professional associations, scientific academies	Membership fees and fees to attend sponsored events
Informatics Europe	Yes	Research and Education in Informatics	mostly universities	Membership fees, conference execution, project-specific contracts
Big Data Value Association	Yes	Big Data	Industry and academia	Membership fees
NESSI	European Technology Platform	Software Services and Data	Industry and academia	Publicly funded projects (e.g. H2020)
NEM New	European Technology Platform	Networked and electronic media	Industry, academia, standardization bodies, government institutions	Publicly funded projects (e.g. H2020)
EOSC	Yes	Scientific data infrastructures	Only legal entities, no individuals; specifically, it is membership in the EOSC Association	Currently only membership fees, but other possibilities are currently being explored in Working Groups.
European Clusters	No	Software Engineering, Cloud, Security	European Projects	None
AI Alliance	No	Artificial Intelligence	Business and consumers organizations, trade unions, academia	None

	Legal entity	Areas of interest	Members' nature	Revenues
Horizon Europe Partnership	To be defined	Different areas covered by Horizon Europe Pillars	Under definition. Depends on the type of partnership	To be defined
European Alliance on Industrial Data and Cloud	To be defined	Cloud computing and data governance	Member states, private and public organizations	None
ECISO	Yes	Cybersecurity	Industry, associations, government institutions	None

From the elements summarized in the table, we have learned the following facts. **Most of the associations have been founded as a legal entity, typical a no-profit organization.**

Each association has a specific focus that constitutes its distinguishing element. Based also on their focus, **some associations aggregate individual members while many others have organizations of various kinds** (enterprises, academic organizations, standardization bodies, ...) **as affiliates.** In all cases, **associations offer multiple networking possibilities to their affiliates and mediate the communication between these and other external stakeholders.**

Even if some associations do not foresee membership fees, **most of them do and identify multiple types of fees for different stakeholders.** **Besides the membership fees, some associations self-sustain offering other services** (e.g., publication services, conference management, the execution of specific projects).

From the governance perspective, almost all associations we have analysed are managed by a board constituted of voluntary members either elected or selected by affiliates. The board typically is on duty for a **fixed term** of two years. In some cases, a mechanism to ensure continuity is established so that every year half of the board members change and the other remain for another year. In the case the affiliates are other organizations, they constitute an assembly that oversees the work of the board.

Interestingly, some of the considered associations have been created by a CSA like SWForum.eu around some specific high priority subject for Europe.

The analysis we have conducted so far gives us some hints concerning the organization of our Forum. **First important points are the identification of a clear mission and focus and the set of target stakeholders;** a preliminary identification of these aspects has been conducted in Section 2 and will be developed further in the next months, based also on the discussion with potential interested partners.

The experience by the other associations shows that it is not inconceivable for the SWForum.eu Living Forum to take into consideration the possibility of creating a non-profit organization. Although it is unlikely that any SWForum.eu group would explicitly hire dependent personnel, it is certainly possible that it could decide to set up a system of membership fees, as well as management of funds to finance conferences, publications, awards, and the like. The creation of a legal entity will also be beneficial to keep the Forum detached from the SWForum.eu project. This will enable the creation of a driving group for the Forum that will be hopefully larger than SWForum.eu partners, thus creating the preconditions for the Forum self-sustainability at the end of the project. It will allow for the participation of other partners and will foster the creation of a proper organizational structure and a bylaw.

As many other organizations, the activities of the Forum could be organized in working groups focusing on specific technical issues, but it will also be appropriate to consider the formation of WGs dedicated to aspects of the Living Forum related to sustainability, and opening membership in these WGs also to participants from the broader community.

5. The Fellowship Programme

The Fellowship Programme aims at involving well-known experts in the activities of the Forum. The fellows will be involved in the cross-fertilization workshops and in the other activities promoted by the Forum. This group of high-profile, acknowledged experts in their respective domains will create an attractive “pull” effect on potential participants in these activities and events and maintain a high level of excellence in the interactions within the Forum. This will increase the possibility for the Forum to have a strong impact on the research and innovation community in Europe.

The Fellowship Programme will be supported by a small fund that we will use to pay a symbolic stipend or refund travel expenses to the research fellows interested in participating in the Forum meetings and activities. and Even if this will not constitute per se an incentive for experts to become fellows, we do hope that it will attract their interest in the Forum activities. The reciprocal interest will then be nurtured by the discussions during the cross-fertilization workshops and we do hope this will result in a long-lasting relation.

SWForum.eu will issue periodic calls for participation to the Fellowship Program and will proactively invite well-known researchers in the subject areas that will be the focus of the Forum activities.

The first call will concern trustworthy software and open source as this will be the topic of the first cross-fertilization workshop we plan to run as inaugural meeting for the Forum. In this workshop we plan to invite experts in trustworthiness and in open source. Other speakers will be reached through a call for contributions that is going to be issued in the next days.

6. Conclusions

This deliverable is the first one of a series reporting the results achieved in Task 3.3 focusing on the creation and organization of a self-sustainable Forum of researchers and practitioners, “the Forum”.

We have reported on the initial goals of the Forum and on a preliminary analysis of associations in areas contiguous to software engineering. This analysis has been conducted based on the knowledge of the SWForum.eu partners and it is not necessarily exhaustive. Its intent is to offer to further thoughts and analyses some exemplary cases of interesting organizations that could be taken as a reference in the definition of the organization, governance structure and business model behind our Forum. The preliminary results of the analysis show that it is possible to establish the Forum as a legal entity and that the Forum could self-sustain through some membership fees, the offering of some services or the participation to funded projects. The analysis also shows that the Forum should have a clear objective and should clearly identify its target group of members. Finally, to ensure the participation by members, it should organize itself in a democratic manner, with a fixed-term governing board elected by all members.

We have also briefly described the approach we plan to follow for what concerns the creation of the Fellowship Programme.

In the following months, in collaboration with Task 2.2, we will organize the first cross-fertilization workshop. It will call the attention of the community on the prominent topic of how to reconcile the concept of trustworthiness with the idea of open source software. We plan to constitute an initial community of interest around this subject so to create the initial kernel of the Forum. Based on the feedback we will obtain by the community, we will define, in cooperation with our counterparts, the short-term workplan of the Forum. This workplan will aim at the creation of a joint publication as a result of the workshop and will guide the next steps toward the institutionalization of the Forum and the definition of its governance structure.